
Bounds for Emanant of Lacunary Type Complex Polynomial

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Abstract Let $p(z)$ be a polynomial of degree n and let α be any real or complex number, then $D_\alpha p(z)$, the polar derivative of $p(z)$, is called by Laguerre [6] the “emanant” of $p(z)$, by Polya and Szegő [8] the “derivative of $p(z)$ with respect to the point α ”, and by Marden [7], simply the “polar derivative” of $p(z)$. It is obviously of interest to obtain estimates concerning growth of $D_\alpha p(z)$. In this paper we prove interesting results for the polar derivative of a lacunary type of polynomial which not only improve upon some earlier known results in the same area but also improve upon a result on ordinary derivative for polynomials in particular case.

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1. Introduction

Let α be a complex number. If $p(z)$ is a polynomial of degree n , then polar derivative of $p(z)$ with respect to point α , denoted by $D_\alpha p(z)$, is defined by

$$D_\alpha p(z) = n p(z) + (\alpha - z) p'(z). \quad (1.1)$$

and

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow \infty} \left[\frac{D_\alpha p(z)}{\alpha} \right] = p'(z). \quad (1.2)$$

It is obviously of interest to obtain estimates concerning the growth of $D_\alpha p(z)$. In this direction Aziz [1] proved several sharp results concerning the maximum modulus of the polar derivative of a polynomial $p(z)$ with restricted zeros.

For the class of polynomials not vanishing in the disc $|z| < k$, $k \geq 1$, Aziz [1] proved the following result for the polar derivative of $p(z)$.

Theorem A. *If $p(z)$ is a polynomial of degree n having no zeros in the disc $|z| < k$, $k \geq 1$, then for every real or complex number α with $|\alpha| \geq 1$,*

$$\max_{|z|=1} |D_{\alpha} p(z)| \leq n \left(\frac{k+|\alpha|}{1+k} \right) \max_{|z|=1} |p(z)|. \quad (1.3)$$

The result is best possible and equality in (1.3) holds for the polynomial $p(z) = (z+k)^n$, with real $\alpha \geq 1$.

As a refinement of Theorem A, Aziz and Shah [2] proved the following result, for the polar derivative of $p(z)$.

Theorem B. If $p(z) = \sum_{j=0}^n a_j z^j$ is a polynomial of degree n having no zero in $|z| < k$, $k \geq 1$, then for every real or complex number α with $|\alpha| \geq 1$,

$$\max_{|z|=1} |D_{\alpha} p(z)| \leq \frac{n}{1+k} \left\{ (|\alpha|+k) \max_{|z|=1} |p(z)| - (|\alpha|-1) \min_{|z|=k} |p(z)| \right\}. \quad (1.4)$$

The result is best possible and extremal polynomial is $p(z) = \left(\frac{z+k}{1+k} \right)^n$ for every real $\alpha \geq k$.

For the class of polynomial $p(z)$ having all its zeros in $|z| \leq 1$, Shah [9] proved the following

Theorem C. If all the zeros of the n^{th} degree polynomial $p(z)$ lie in $|z| \leq 1$, then for every real or complex number α with $|\alpha| \geq 1$,

$$\max_{|z|=1} |D_{\alpha} p(z)| \geq \frac{n}{2} (|\alpha|-1) \max_{|z|=1} |p(z)|. \quad (1.5)$$

The result is sharp and extremal polynomial is $p(z) = (z-1)^n$ with real $\alpha \geq 1$.

For the class of polynomial $p(z)$ having all its zeros in $|z| \leq 1$, Shah [9] extended Turán's Theorem to the polar derivative of the polynomial and proved the following.

Theorem D. If all the zeros of the n^{th} degree polynomial $p(z)$ lie in $|z| \leq 1$, then for every real or complex number α with $|\alpha| \geq 1$,

$$\max_{|z|=1} |D_{\alpha} p(z)| \geq \frac{n}{2} (|\alpha|-1) \max_{|z|=1} |p(z)|. \quad (1.6)$$

The result is sharp and extremal polynomial is $p(z) = (z-1)^n$ with real $\alpha \geq 1$

As a generalization of Theorem D, Aziz and Rather [3] proved the following result for the polar derivative of a polynomial $p(z)$.

Theorem E. If $p(z)$ is a polynomial of degree n having all its zeros in $|z| \leq k$, $k \leq 1$, then for every real or complex number α with $|\alpha| \geq k$,

$$\max_{|z|=1} |D_{\alpha} p(z)| \geq n \left(\frac{|\alpha|-k}{1+k} \right) \max_{|z|=1} |p(z)|. \quad (1.7)$$

Inequality (1.7) is best possible and equality occurs for $p(z) = (z-k)^n$ with real $\alpha \geq k$.

2. Main Theorem

For the class of Lacunary type of polynomials $p(z) = a_n z^n + \sum_{j=\mu}^n a_{n-j} z^{n-j}$, $1 \leq \mu \leq n$, we prove the following result which gives a generalization as well as an improvement of Theorem E.

Theorem 2.1. If $p(z) = a_n z^n + \sum_{j=\mu}^n a_{n-j} z^{n-j}$, $1 \leq \mu \leq n$, is a polynomial of degree n having all its zeros in

$|z| \leq k$, $k \leq 1$, then for every real or complex number α with $|\alpha| \geq k^\mu$, we have

$$\max_{|z|=1} |D_\alpha p(z)| \geq n \left(\frac{|\alpha| - k^\mu}{1 + k^\mu} \right) \max_{|z|=1} |p(z)| + \frac{n}{k^{n-\mu}} \left(\frac{|\alpha| + 1}{1 + k^\mu} \right) \min_{|z|=k} |p(z)| \quad (2.1)$$

Dividing both sides of (2.1) by $|\alpha|$, letting $|\alpha| \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain the following generalization of a result due to Govil [4].

Corollary 2.2. If $p(z) = a_n z^n + \sum_{j=\mu}^n a_{n-j} z^{n-j}$, $1 \leq \mu \leq n$, is a polynomial of degree n having all its zeros in

$|z| \leq k$, $k \leq 1$, then we have

$$\max_{|z|=1} |p'(z)| \geq \frac{n}{1 + k^\mu} \left\{ \max_{|z|=1} |p(z)| + \frac{1}{k^{n-\mu}} \min_{|z|=k} |p(z)| \right\}. \quad (2.2)$$

The result is sharp and extremal polynomial is $p(z) = (z^\mu + k^\mu)^{\frac{n}{\mu}}$, where n is a multiple of μ .

For $\mu = 1$, inequality (2.1) reduces to the following result due to Govil and Mc Tume[5].

Corollary 2.3. If $p(z) = \sum_{j=0}^n a_j z^j$ is a polynomial of degree n having all its zeros in $|z| \leq k$, $k \leq 1$, then for

every real or complex number α with $|\alpha| \geq k$, we have

$$\max_{|z|=1} |D_\alpha p(z)| \geq n \left(\frac{|\alpha| - k}{1 + k} \right) \max_{|z|=1} |p(z)| + \frac{n}{k^{n-1}} \left(\frac{|\alpha| + 1}{1 + k} \right) \min_{|z|=k} |p(z)|. \quad (2.3)$$

The inequality is sharp and equality holds for $p(z) = (z - k)^n$ with real $\alpha \geq k$.

3. Lemmas

For the proofs of the theorems, we need the following lemmas.

Lemma 3.1. Let $p(z)$ be polynomial of degree n and α is any real or complex number with $|\alpha| \neq 0$. Then for

$|z| = 1$,

$$|D_\alpha q(z)| = \left| n \bar{\alpha} p(z) + (1 - \bar{\alpha} z) p'(z) \right|. \quad (3.1)$$

where $q(z) = z^n p\left(\frac{1}{z}\right)$.

The above lemma is due to Aziz [1].

Lemma 3.2. If all the zeros of an n^{th} degree polynomial $p(z)$ lie in $|z| \leq k$, then for $|\alpha| \geq k$, the polar derivative $D_\alpha p(z)$ of $p(z)$ at point α also has all its zeros in $|z| \leq k$.

The above lemma is due to Marden [7].

Lemma 3.3. Let $p(z) = a_0 + \sum_{\nu=\mu}^n a_\nu z^\nu, 1 \leq \mu \leq n$, be a polynomial of degree n not vanishing in $|z| < k, k \geq 1$,

and $q(z) = z^n \overline{p\left(\frac{1}{\bar{z}}\right)}$. Then for $|z| = 1$ and $R \geq 1$,

$$k^\mu |p(Rz) - p(z)| \leq |q(Rz) - q(z)| - (R^n - 1) \min_{|z|=k} |p(z)|. \tag{3.2}$$

The above lemma is due to Aziz and Rather [3].

Lemma 3.4. Let $p(z) = a_n z^n + \sum_{j=\mu}^n a_{n-j} z^{n-j}, 1 \leq \mu \leq n$, be a polynomial of degree n having all its zeros in

$|z| \leq k, k \leq 1$. Then for $|z| = 1$ and $R \geq 1$

$$k^\mu |p(Rz) - p(z)| \geq |q(Rz) - q(z)| + \frac{(R^n - 1)}{k^{n-\mu}} \min_{|z|=k} |p(z)|. \tag{3.3}$$

where $q(z) = z^n \overline{p\left(\frac{1}{\bar{z}}\right)}$.

Proof of Lemma 3.4. Since $p(z)$ has all its zeros in $|z| \leq k, k \leq 1$, then $q(z) = z^n \overline{p\left(\frac{1}{\bar{z}}\right)}$ has all its zeros in

$|z| \geq \frac{1}{k}, \frac{1}{k} \geq 1$. On applying Lemma 3.3 to $q(z)$, we get for $|z| = 1$,

$$\frac{1}{k^\mu} |q(Rz) - q(z)| \leq |p(Rz) - p(z)| - (R^n - 1) \min_{|z|=\frac{1}{k}} |q(z)| \tag{3.4}$$

But

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{|z|=\frac{1}{k}} |q(z)| &= \min_{|z|=\frac{1}{k}} \left| z^n \overline{p\left(\frac{1}{\bar{z}}\right)} \right| = \min_{|z|=1} \left| \frac{z^n}{k^n} \overline{p\left(\frac{k}{\bar{z}}\right)} \right| \\ &= \frac{1}{k^n} \min_{|z|=1} |p(kz)| = \frac{1}{k^n} \min_{|z|=k} |p(z)|. \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

Combining inequalities (3.4) and (3.5), we get

$$\frac{1}{k^\mu} |q(Rz) - q(z)| \leq |p(Rz) - p(z)| - \frac{(R^n - 1)}{k^n} \min_{|z|=k} |p(z)|,$$

from which Lemma 3.4 follows.

From the above lemma, we deduce the following result, by dividing both sides of inequality (3.3) by $(R-1)$ and let $R \rightarrow 1$, which is also of independent interest.

Lemma 3.5. Let $p(z) = a_n z^n + \sum_{j=\mu}^n a_{n-j} z^{n-j}, 1 \leq \mu \leq n$, be a polynomial of degree n having all its zeros in

$|z| \leq k, k \leq 1$. Then for $|z| = 1$

$$k^\mu |p'(z)| \geq |q'(z)| + \frac{n}{k^{n-\mu}} \min_{|z|=k} |p(z)|. \quad (3.6)$$

where $q(z) = z^n \overline{p\left(\frac{1}{\bar{z}}\right)}$.

4. Proof of the Main Theorem

Proof of Theorem 2.1. Let $q(z) = z^n \overline{p\left(\frac{1}{\bar{z}}\right)}$. Then it can be easily verified that for $|z|=1$,

$$|q'(z)| = |np(z) - zp'(z)| \quad (4.1)$$

Now for $|z|=1$, we have from (4.1)

$$\begin{aligned} |np(z)| &= |np(z) - zp'(z) + zp'(z)| \\ &\leq |np(z) - zp'(z)| + |p'(z)| = |q'(z)| + |p'(z)|. \end{aligned} \quad (4.2)$$

Inequality (4.2) when combined with Lemma 3.5, gives for $|z|=1$,

$$|p'(z)| \geq \frac{n}{1+k^\mu} |p(z)| + \frac{nm}{k^{n-\mu}(1+k^\mu)}. \quad (4.3)$$

where $m = \min_{|z|=k} |p(z)|$.

Now for every real or complex number α , we have

$$D_\alpha p(z) = np(z) + (\alpha - z)p'(z).$$

This gives for $|z|=1$,

$$\begin{aligned} |D_\alpha p(z)| &\geq |\alpha| |p'(z)| - |np(z) - zp'(z)| \\ &= |\alpha| |p'(z)| - |q'(z)|. \end{aligned} \quad (4.4)$$

Now on combining inequality (4.4) with Lemma 3.5, we get for $|z|=1$.

$$|D_\alpha p(z)| \geq (|\alpha| - k^\mu) |p'(z)| + \frac{nm}{k^{n-\mu}}. \quad (4.5)$$

Inequality (4.3), when combined with above inequality (4.5), gives for $|z|=1$,

$$|D_\alpha p(z)| \geq (|\alpha| - k^\mu) \left\{ \frac{n}{1+k^\mu} |p(z)| + \frac{nm}{k^{n-\mu}(1+k^\mu)} \right\} + \frac{nm}{k^{n-\mu}}.$$

which on simplification gives for $|z|=1$,

$$|D_\alpha p(z)| \geq n \left(\frac{|\alpha| - k^\mu}{1+k^\mu} \right) |p(z)| + \frac{n(|\alpha| + 1)}{k^{n-\mu}(1+k^\mu)} m.$$

from which Theorem 2.1 follows easily.

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